

Transcription of Interview 1

*for Shane Murphy
December 2020*

Shane: We shouldn't be too long.

Interviewee: No, it's fine, you're welcome. We're busy, but I think, also, this actually sound important.. actually, not sound, because you have already enrolled, so we need to do it for you to meet your academic obligations.

Shane: Yes, thanks so much. So Mr #####, there's only four overarching questions, so please feel free to share whatever comes to mind; and it's largely just to get your views and opinions, from a manager's perspective. So the first one is, quite broadly, what are your views on National Health Insurance?

Interviewee: Okay. My view is, you'll have the integrated system that will operate at a national level, in which funds will be made available by the state, and by so doing, it will actually ensure that all citizens have equal opportunity to healthcare. And I think, from where I'm sitting, it will also assist on [...] to health facility, but also the issue of capability; because it means you'll have people who are well-trained, especially on a primary healthcare level. Because I understand what it's bringing, is to ensure that all our health professionals at primary healthcare, will be trained, in order for them to respond well, to service needs.

And then, the other thing, is the issue of overcrowding on public institutions, I think it will also reduce that, and ensure that we share equal numbers of patients with private, which will actually reduce on the number of litigation, that happened in the past, due to workload, where you end up having employees who have overworked themselves, and as a result of fatigue, it results on a litigation, because of some medical non-compliance or clinical under-performance. So I think, actually, it will assist a lot, based on those issues.

Shane: Okay. And what is your view on the way that NHI will, or should, be funded? (repeat) What is your view on the funding scheme of the NHI?

Interviewee: Okay. I think my view is, all tax payers, even though they'll not be directly affected, for now, they'll later be affected, because if you are an economically active citizen, and you stand to be taxed, I think, on a later date, once the scheme is established, we'll benchmark with other countries like Ghana; I do not even want to go outside the continent. I think, lately, you'll have to be taxed, though the tax will be reasonable. But for now, I think the government will be responsible for funding it, until the scheme is well-established.

So my view is, yes, it will actually affect tax payers, but at the same time, it will be **with** relief to the very same tax payers, because we will have equal access to health facilities, whether you are economic active, no matter how much you earn, you'll actually have the opportunity to be treated the same. So I believe that the funding, even though it will actually focus on those people who will be economically active, whether you are a business person, or employed **by** somebody, will actually equally contribute, so that the scheme is well-established.

It will not actually operate like what happened with GEMS, because when GEMS started, there were a lot of promises that actually **to relieve** a lot of people, since it's a government employee medical scheme, but later GEMS changed to behave like more or less the same with other private owned medical scheme, like Bonitas.

[05:09]

So in terms of medical health, I think National Health Insurance, I believe that it will be, actually, easily managed, since the funds will **remain** centralised at national level, where all administrative work will be done. I think, when tax is collected, the Minister of Finance, and other ministers who are involved on the management or administration of finances, will be involved. So I don't think it will, later, change to behaving the same manner that GEMS is behaving.

Shane: Okay. And one of the ways that the scheme would like to operate, is to do the strategic purchasing, where they separate the provider from the funder; and so the money that is pooled into NHI, would be given to an independent body, that would then purchase from public and private. What is your views on that setup? Do you think that's a good.. or do you see any shortfalls, of it?

Interviewee: I don't think it's a good idea. We have already experienced, with **regard to health**, where service providers are encouraged, or are used, to render services for the state, it's actually open to abuse, in a way that prices will not be managed or controlled; you'll have a very serious issue of quality, value for money will be compromised. So my belief is, we still need public service that are well-trained, or to deal with all matters related to National Health Insurance.

Experience has taught me that those service providers, they tend to actually get less quality, as I've indicated that, less quality on products that are supplied. So I think the problem will continue; the issue of kickbacks will continue; because, for a service provider to get a tender, we'll have to pay something, as a kickback. So to do away with this thing of where there'll be less value for money, I think we just need to make it a point that we in-source it, and government takes over; we do not involve any private issues.

Shane: Okay. So you feel it would be safest for government to run the purchasing of services, both within public and private sectors?

Interviewee: I think it will be safe for government to do that, based on what I've experienced. The private sectors, they'll be, actually, assisting, in which they'll come and receive whatever is being procured by government, in that it will also avoid an issue, where you'll have different prices, public versus private. But once you open it to private, or to service provider, prices will actually fluctuate, based on those things that I've mentioned, which is pure corruption. So I believe on centralising, resourcing, and having well-trained personnel, who will deal with public and private, but being appointed by the public.

Shane: Okay. And Mr #####, what is your views on working together with the private sector?

Interviewee: I think that's what I like, because I feel disturbed, sometimes, because I feel that even though some of us in government, we do not have those financial **measures**, but based on the fact that

we've got a opportunity and a privilege to actually contribute to medical schemes. When you visit private, you see the type of services that you receive, so I feel that if we start working together, it will be easy, in which we'll be able to share resources, in which we'll be able to share skills. I think, even to ensure that citizens have equal access, whether to private or public.

[10:00]

I want to give you an example; it was a coincidence, where I was in the Vaal, and I visited a private hospital. I was treated by the same nurse, on that day, and it happened again, that I had to visit the very same hospital, where I was working at, and the very same nurse, coincidentally, she had to service me. The behaviour was different in terms of how I was treated, let alone the services that she rendered on those two days. The behaviour, how she welcomed me, on private, it was very much different from how I was treated when I arrive at public institution. Then I asked her, after all those things, and she said to me, it's because of workload; I'm frustrated before nine o'clock, because I have to stand and attend to more than fifty people, which is against the patient ratio that a nurse must see in a day. And then I ask in private, in private I'll be allocated only five; and that doesn't actually **heal how** [...] **actually live, or these** [...] **the nurses**.

So in other words, I want to say that, sharing, equal sharing of resources, equal sharing of resources in terms of skills, in terms of physical resources, in terms of medical equipment, in terms of private and public must share resources; whether it's funding, or whatsoever, so that they are equally empowered to render services, or best services to our citizens.

Shane: Okay. And then, Mr #####, have you had any engagement with government, on NHI policy development, or any communications, or feedback?

Interviewee: No, actually, I didn't have any engagement, because we're not afforded with that opportunity. I think people who are at **provincial** level, yes, at some point, they did actually attend and where they were given inputs. But I feel, how it was done, the engagement part, or the consultative part, was not done enough. Because, in terms of **skills**, where people who are at receiving end of service delivery, or at the coalface of service delivery, I feel that it was necessary for them to go to clinic levels, for them to come to district level, actually, institutional level, or whatever level, to engage and to request for our inputs. I think it was not done properly, however, I still support the idea, because, when I went through the document, I'm convinced that, yes, we'll have **gap**, like any other policy that is new, but later, we'll actually review and learn and move forward.

Shane: Yes. Why do you think that government didn't engage at district and sub-district level?

Interviewee: I think when you compile any policy that affects HR, because this have direct impact; I'll give you an example of HR, because in that case, we were supposed to have been given the opportunity to actually explain the challenges that we face, at public facilities, and then make proposal, or give inputs, as to how do you want National Health Insurance to function, in HR perspective, because we're their support service, and how do you actually want skills to be distributed. I think it will also assist, because we know very well, that we have got enough skills in the **level** market, but some of the skills are reluctant to come to public, if, maybe, we afford it. And then the issue of where you have, for

instance, a doctor who is work in private, at the same time, working at public institution, the impact it has on service delivery; if we engage, we are actually going to give such things, so that they are not repeated during the implementation.

However, I saw, and believe that it is covered by the fact that we will be able to share resources, but I still feel that consultation was supposed to have happened, so that they get the challenges that people who are at coalface of service delivery, and how we currently struggle to attack some of the skill, to government, due to people prefer private, for some of the reasons that I've already mentioned, workload and lack of medical equipment or resources.

[15:02]

Shane: Ja. And Mr #####, you spoke about people working at the coalface, how do you think that most people get - or yourself, as well – your information on the National Health Insurance? Are there directives that are given? Or is it largely social media and news?

Interviewee: How did I get to know it?

Shane: Ja, or most of your updates and information and processes, going forward; is there a channel that you receive information? Or do you follow the media, to get your information?

Interviewee: I think 50% is the media, 50%.. I'm privileged that I receive emails, every day, from.. I'll say, maybe 30%, it's emails that are sent with presentation, from national to [...] distributed to institutions; not for us to give input, but for us to empower ourselves.

And then the other thing is, my own research, the remaining 20%; because immediately, when I've learnt about it, then I have to go to internet and research more. As I've indicated, that I was actually looking at countries like Ghana, how they did it; and I've actually checked with other countries like the United States. So we're not actually.. it's just emails, as I've said, and then internet, and media.

Shane: Okay. And then, Mr #####, your perception about the readiness of the public service, to implement National Health Insurance; how would you assess the current healthcare infrastructure?

Interviewee: Okay, the infrastructure-wise, we're not ready, at all. We're not ready, because I'll continue to compare ourselves, or the public service with private. Even today, if you go to a private hospital, and go back to public, you'll see that we are not ready, from the receiving point, which is the reception, we are not ready; so we still need to improve and work on our infrastructure. You have infrastructures that are very old, the ageing issue is very serious. You cannot be sitting with a hospital that is built fifty years back, and you want to start something that is more technologically, on that infrastructure. So I believe that we have very few infrastructures that are available, to can implement, but 90% of them are very old, so they are not ready.

Shane: Okay. And do you think any other.. human resources, why.. do you think that's ready for NHI?

Interviewee: Again, on human resources, there are not enough awareness, due to fact that if you go to a nursing assistant or staff nurse, they're, unlike myself, who's sitting in an office, and I'll go on read through it to empower myself; those people, they do not know much about it, and the problem is, we

want to start training them, when the National Health [...], we were supposed to start preparing them, in terms of skills, even though we do not directly talk to it. But we know exactly, if I talk about primary healthcare, National Health Insurance will work differently from the current model, whereby you're required to do things, at some point, digitally. So if we start preparing them today, so that when the time for implementation arrives, we just start training them on what exactly should be done. But generally, on those technological issues, how to respond to all those technological needs, we haven't done enough; and I foresee danger, whereby we will implement with people who are not well capacitated. So if we start today, before implementation, I believe employees will be ready for implementation.

Shane: Okay. And what do you think are some of the biggest challenges for district health service managers, to cope with contracting, in NHI?

Interviewee: You mean the challenges that they'll face?

Shane: Ja, to implement NHI?

Interviewee: I think I've already mentioned, the first one, is the infrastructure; the second one, is the medical equipment, because we should have started now, procuring all those medical equipment that are required. Even though we're not going to utilising them directly, but starting to work on them, in some form, we'd be doing a, so-called, on the job training, and trying to ensure that people understand.

[20:16]

I think, on the issue of medical equipment, it will be a huge challenge; the infrastructure, we have already mentioned. And then, I think the other thing that will actually have a problem, is the issue of leadership, because less number of leaders, at the sub-district level, or at district level, are empowered.

And when I look, the other thing, is the ageing, because at **the time**, you have got.. there are some district manager, or district manager who is very old, and for you to actually retrain or upskill that person, to behave in line with the current need of National Health Insurance, it will be difficult.

What we're supposed to be doing now, is to do a succession planning, and align it to National Health Insurance. In this case, you see, as I sit here, I was born before technology; it means within HR, if I talk of HR, you must do a succession plan that will fairly identify two people, who will be ready to take over when I leave, and are well-capacitated to respond to all needs of National Health. So I think succession plan-wise, and aligning our skills to National Health, we are not doing enough.

Shane: Mr #####, why do you think we are lagging behind, or not doing enough? What do you think, is it a lack of will, a lack of resources? Ja, I'm not sure.

Interviewee: No, actually, it cannot be lack of resources, because the commitment was supposed to start at national level; that is a political decision, whereby the Minister of Finance will be instructed to allocate funds. I think, by now, we should have started by piloting, even if we arrive in a hospital, and we take a number of people - even if there are thirty - and institutions start piloting; specifically for piloting, not for the **near** service delivery. And then we start, that will actually give us the experience, at

what challenges that we'll actually encounter. So I believe that we **will want** to start implementing, without doing proper piloting projects; so that's where I think we are **late**. There is no enough budget, that is allocated and mandated, which is given from the politicians, who's the President and his cabinet, to other heads of department or other executive authority, to say, start piloting, especially on health, start piloting on health facilities. If Johannesburg district can have three facilities that are identified, and pilot systems start; you know, you rather lose money on pilot projects, it will be less than to lose on implementation.

Shane: There have been a few pilot projects, in various districts, are you aware of them, or have received any feedback from them?

Interviewee: Yes, I'm aware, I remember even when I was at Tswana [...], few people who were taken for training, and those people they came back, and they started implementing what they were taught, but I don't believe it was done enough. A pilot must be taken seriously, and in terms of HR, immediately, when they started piloting, we're supposed to be called and receive feedback on the challenges encountered, in relation to human resources, because we are a HR support service.

In terms of finances, finance was supposed to be called, and they'd be actually empowered of what was the challenges encountered, during the pilot. So you cannot have a pilot project that is not actually communicated to the whole management, or to the specialists who are there to support the project. So yes, it might have been done, but I believe it was not done in the correct way.

And finally, it was supposed to be documented, as to how the project.. actually, in a form of document, it's where you have a pilot, because when you start the pilot, they must start monitoring, evaluation and end date; so that it was supposed to be documented, so that it formed part of baseline, as to where we start. So we don't have such document that is signed by our executive authority, to show that pilot were implemented in some way.

[25:11]

Shane: Okay. And Mr #####, my last question, is there any other view or thought, that you would like to express on the NHI?

Interviewee: Yes, I think what I like to impress, is I'll appreciate if, by the next financial year, we'll have a commitment from the physical point of view, the Minister of Finance, or the national cabinet as well, try to put aside, budget, for a continuous piloting, until we are convinced that we are ready, before implementation is done. Because I'm afraid if piloting is not done properly, we will end up losing money or funds, to things that will not work. So that's my only idea.

And in terms of HR, I also wish to see that most people, maybe 10% of each facility, are trained, specifically on National Health Insurance; and not from one discipline, it must be a multi-tasked or disciplinary team, from HR finance supply chain, nursing, clinicians, and management; all of them must be trained on how to implement, and these people must also form part of **monitoring team**, at the provincial level, of pilot projects, which are already enrolled, and also to finally document and circulate it, nationally, so that people learn from it.

Shane: Okay. Then done with the interview, Mr #####, thanks so much for your time, and your valuable insight.

Interviewee: No, I really actually, appreciate, because at least you have challenged my mind, so that I think, after this interview, my behaviour will be totally different from what I believe, **against** National Health Insurance, and I think you have challenged me to further research in terms of the readiness, and in terms of the skills that I'll need, before implementation. Thank you so much. And I'm sorry that we had to postpone number of times.

Shane: No worries at all.

Interviewee: I'm sorry, ja.

Shane: I'll keep you updated with the results of the research, as well.

Interviewee: No, good luck with your studies.

Shane: Thanks so much Mr #####, have a good day.

Interviewee: Enjoy **the rest**.

Shane: Bye.

Interviewee: Thank you. Bye.

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